

FRACTURE SIMULATION OF COMPOSITE MATERIAL BY FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

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Mechanical behavior of composite materials (fiber reinforced plastics) was investigated by one of the authors and Poisson's ratio was found to be a function of the applied stress and this is very special phenomenon which occurs only in composite materials. Such phenomenon probably is governed by the state of deformation in composites. In other words, the fibers in composites are able to deform at low stress level, while the resin is broken and the fibers can not deform at high stress level.

From the above experimental point of view, it is clear that Poisson's ratio can not be constant in the elastic region for composite materials. Therefore, the authors consider that fracture of composites may be described by its Poisson's ratio. On the basis of this assumption, the following fracture parameter is proposed;

$$FV = \int_0^{\sigma_B} (\nu_{xy}^* + \nu_{yx}^*) d\sigma_x$$

where σ_B and σ_x are the breaking stress and the applied stress, respectively and FV is called as the fracture value.

ν_{xy}^* and ν_{yx}^* are equivalent Poisson's ratio which have the stress dependency.

Above equation is thus proposed as the fracture criterion for composite materials, namely when FV reaches a critical value, the composite materials fracture.

The relation between FV and the applied stress for unidirectional fiber-glass reinforced plastics is calculated and the numerical solution of the fracture stress for unidirectional FRP is obtained as the function of the fiber orientation. Additionally, crack propagation of FRP is investigated by using FV and finite element technique.

As a result of this study, it became evident that FV can be used as a fracture criterion for composite materials, because fracture simulation is in good agreement with the experimental results.

Introduction

Mechanical behavior of composite materials (fiber reinforced plastics) was investigated by one of the authors and Poisson's ratio was found to be a function of the applied stress and this is very special phenomenon which occurs only in composite materials. Such phenomenon probably is governed by the state of deformation in composites. In other words, the fibers in composites are able to deform at low stress level, while the resin is broken and the fibers can not deform at high stress level.

Stress - Strain Relation in Orthotropic Laminate

The fundamental system of linear elasticity for orthotropic laminate is described as follows;

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \epsilon_x &= C_{11}\sigma_x + C_{12}\sigma_y + C_{13}\tau_{xy} \\ \epsilon_y &= C_{12}\sigma_x + C_{22}\sigma_y + C_{23}\tau_{xy} \\ \epsilon_{xy} &= C_{13}\sigma_x + C_{23}\sigma_y + C_{33}\tau_{xy} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (1)$$

Where, C_{ij} are coefficients of compliance which are;

$$\left. \begin{aligned} C_{11} &= \frac{\ell^4}{E_L} + \frac{m^4}{E_T} + \ell^2 m^2 \left(\frac{1}{G_{LT}} - \frac{2\nu_{LT}}{E_L} \right) \\ C_{22} &= \frac{m^4}{E_L} + \frac{\ell^4}{E_T} = \ell^2 m^2 \left(\frac{1}{G_{LT}} - \frac{2\nu_{LT}}{E_L} \right) \\ C_{33} &= \frac{1}{G_{LT}} + 4\ell^2 m^2 \left(\frac{1}{E_L} + \frac{1}{E_T} + \frac{2\nu_{LT}}{E_L} - \frac{1}{G_{LT}} \right) \\ C_{12} &= \frac{\nu_{LT}}{E_L} + \ell^2 m^2 \left(\frac{1}{E_L} + \frac{1}{E_T} + \frac{2\nu_{LT}}{E_L} - \frac{1}{G_{LT}} \right) \\ C_{13} &= -2\ell^3 m \left(\frac{1+\nu_{LT}}{E_L} \right) + 2\ell m^3 \left(\frac{1+\nu_{LT}}{E_T} \right) + \ell m (\ell^2 - m^2) \frac{1}{G_{LT}} \\ C_{23} &= -2\ell m^3 \left(\frac{1+\nu_{LT}}{E_L} \right) + 2\ell^3 m \left(\frac{1+\nu_{LT}}{E_T} \right) - \ell m (\ell^2 - m^2) \frac{1}{G_{LT}} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (2)$$

and $\ell = \cos\theta$, $m = \sin\theta$, and θ is the fiber orientation.

For uniaxial tension, stress - strain relations are represented as follows;

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \epsilon_x &= C_{11}\sigma_x, \\ \epsilon_y &= C_{12}\sigma_x, \\ \tau_{xy} &= C_{13}\sigma_x. \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

Hence, the Poisson's ratio is

$$\nu_{xy} = -\frac{\epsilon_y}{\epsilon_x} = -\frac{C_{12}}{C_{11}}$$

$$= \frac{\frac{\nu_T}{E_L} - \ell^2 m^2 \left(\frac{1}{E_L} + \frac{1}{E_T} + \frac{2\nu_{LT}}{E_L} - \frac{1}{G_{LT}} \right)}{\frac{\ell^4}{E_L} + \frac{m^4}{E_T} + \ell^2 m^2 \left(\frac{1}{G_{LT}} - \frac{2\nu_{LT}}{E_L} \right)} \quad (4)$$

Where, E_L , E_T are the moduli of elasticity, G_{LT} is the modulus of elasticity in shear, ν_{LT} is the Poisson's ratio and ϵ_x , ϵ_y are the normal strains, γ_{xy} is the shearing strain and ν_{xy} is the Poisson's ratio for an arbitrary direction.

Fig. 1 Mechanical Model for Composite Material.

Stress - Strain Relation for Visco - Elasto - Plastic Mechanical Model

The mechanical model which has been presented for composite materials is shown in Fig. 1. ⁽¹⁾ For this model the stress-strain relation is:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \epsilon_x &= \frac{\sigma_x}{E_x^*} - \nu_{yx}^* \frac{\sigma_y}{E_y^*}, \\ \epsilon_y &= -\nu_{xy}^* \frac{\sigma_x}{E_x^*} + \frac{\sigma_y}{E_y^*}, \\ \tau_{xy} &= \frac{\tau_{xy}}{G_{xy}^*}, \end{aligned} \right\} (5)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} E_x^* &= E_x + \frac{1}{S_x}, \\ E_y^* &= E_y + \frac{1}{S_y}, \\ S_x &= \alpha_x e^{n_x \sigma}, \\ S_y &= \alpha_y e^{n_y \sigma}, \end{aligned} \right\} (6)$$

Where, E_x^* , E_y^* are equivalent elastic moduli, ν_{xy}^* , ν_{yx}^* are equivalent Poisson's ratio, E_x , E_y are spring constants and S_x , S_y are coefficient of slider in the mechanical model.

In Eq. (6), α_x and α_y are coefficients of wettability of the resin and n_x , n_y are coefficients which represent the degree of progression of failure. These coefficients can be determined from the σ - ϵ diagram which is obtained by unidirectional tests. When the material is tested unidirectionally, the relation between the stress and the strain is

$$\sigma = E_x^* \epsilon \quad (7)$$

Therefore, E_x^* can be obtained from the values σ and ϵ on the stress-strain diagram and E_x can be also obtained from the slope of σ - ϵ diagram immediately before fracture. The relation between σ - ϵ diagram and these coefficients is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 σ - ϵ Diagram and Coefficients of Spring and Slider

From Eqs. (4) and (5), the Poisson's ratio for two dimensional visco-elasto-plastic mechanical model can be represented by

$$\nu_{xy}^* = \frac{\frac{\nu_{LT}^*}{E_L^*} - \ell^2 m^2 \left(\frac{1}{E_L^*} + \frac{1}{E_T^*} + \frac{2\nu_{LT}^*}{G_{LT}^*} - \frac{1}{G_{LT}^*} \right)}{\frac{\ell^4}{E_L^*} + \frac{m^4}{E_T^*} + \ell^2 m^2 \left(\frac{1}{G_{LT}^*} - \frac{2\nu_{LT}^*}{E_L^*} \right)} \quad (8)$$

Additionally, Maxwell's reciprocity theorem yields

$$\frac{\nu_{xy}^*}{E_x^*} = \frac{\nu_{yx}^*}{E_y^*} \quad (9)$$

Experimentally determined Poisson's ratio for fiberglass reinforced plastic is shown in Fig. 3. The Poisson's ratio in this figure changes rapidly at low applied stress and remains constant at high applied stress. Such phenomenon probably is governed by the geometrical deformation of a composite. In other words, the fiber in composites is able to move smoothly at low applied stress, while the resin is broken and the fiber can not move so smoothly at high applied stress. When the fiber is orientated about 45 degree to the load direction, the Poisson's ratio gradually changes because the fibers move in a sissor like motion.

Fig. 3 Poisson's Ratio and Applied Stress.

Figure 4 shows a numerical analysis of the stress dependency of Poisson's ratio for each fiber orientations. Poisson's ratios for various fiber orientations at low stress are enlarged and shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 4 Numerical Analysis of Stress Dependency of Poisson's Ratio for various Fiber Orientations.

Fig. 5 Poisson's Ratio for Various Fiber Orientations at Low Applied Stress.

For composite materials where geometrical deformation is significant, the Poisson's ratio can not assumed to be constant in the elastic region.

The authors thus considered that fracture of composites may be described by its Poisson's ratio. With this assumption, the following equation is derived.

$$\begin{aligned}
 FV &= \int_0^{\sigma_B} \left| \frac{\epsilon_y}{\epsilon_x} \right| + \left| \frac{\epsilon_x}{\epsilon_y} \right| d\sigma_x, \\
 &= \int_0^{\sigma_B} (\nu_{xy}^* + \nu_{yx}^*) d\sigma_x,
 \end{aligned}$$

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where, σ_B and σ_x are the breaking stress and applied stress, respectively and FV is the fracture value. This relation between Poisson's ratios and FV is shown in Fig. 6. Eq.(10) is thus proposed as the fracture criterion for composite materials, namely, when Eq.(10) reaches a certain value, we consider that the composite material is fractured. For example, Fig. 7 shows the calculated relation between fracture value (FV) and applied stress for unidirectional fiberglass reinforced plastic in terms of the degree of fiber orientation and load direction.

Fracture Simulation

As the Poisson's ratio for unidirectionally fiber reinforced plastics approaches 0.3, the fracture value (FV) which is suggested in this paper becomes

$$FV \approx 300. \tag{11}$$

Fig. 6 Poisson's Ratio and Fracture Value (FV)

The fracture stress for each fiber orientation when FV equals 300 can be calculated from Eqs. (8) and (11).

Figure 8 shows numerical results between the fracture stress and the fiber orientation for unidirectionally fiberglass reinforced plastics. This relation has been investigated by many researchers. Figure 9 shows the experimental results which are obtained by Tsai⁽²⁾ and Norita et. al.⁽³⁾

These figure show that fracture simulation based on Poisson's ratio agrees well with experimental results.

Fig. 7 Calculated Relation between FV and Applied Stress with the Fiber Orientation as a Parameter

Fig. 8 Numerical Relation between Fracture Stress and Fiber Orientation for Unidirectional Reinforced Plastics

It is also noted that modulus of elasticity depends on the applied stress. Figure 10 shows the relation between the fiber orientation and the modulus of elasticity with the applied stress as a parameter. When the applied stress is low, the value of E_x^*/E_L reaches a minimum. This phenomenon can be explained as follows.

From Eq. (2), we have

$$C_{11} = \frac{\cos^4 \theta}{E_L} + \frac{\sin^4 \theta}{E_T} + \cos^2 \theta \sin^2 \theta \left(\frac{1}{G_{LT}} - \frac{2\nu_{LT}}{E_L} \right) \quad (12)$$

And thus

$$\frac{E_L}{E_x^*} = \cos^4 \theta + A \sin^4 \theta + B \cos^2 \theta \sin^2 \theta \quad , \quad (13)$$

where $A = E_L/E_T$, $B = E_L/G_{LT} - 2\nu_{LT}$.

The first differentiation of Eq. (13) with respect to θ yields

$$\left(\frac{E_L}{E_x^*} \right)' = 2 \cos \theta \sin \theta \{ \cos^2 \theta (B-2) + \sin^2 \theta (2A-B) \} \quad (14)$$

Fig. 9 Experimental Result for Unidirectional Fiber Reinforced Plastics obtained by Tsai and N_orita et al.

Therefore, when θ equals 0° , 90° and $\tan^{-1} \sqrt{\frac{B-2}{B-2A}}$

Eq. (13) has maximum or minimum.

The second differentiation of Eq. (13) with respect to θ is

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{E_L}{E_x} \right)'' &= 4 \frac{(B-2A)}{(B-2)} \sin^4 \theta \{ B^2 - B(4+3A) + 2A^2 + 5A + 3 \}, \\ &= 4 \frac{(B-2A)}{(B-2)} D \sin^4 \theta, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where, $D = B^2 - B(4+3A) + 2A^2 + 5A + 3$.

Signs of Eq. (15) for the above θ are as follows;

(i) For $B > 2$, $B > 2A$

$$D = B^2 - B(4+3A) + 2A^2 + 5A + 3, \quad (16)$$

$$< 3 \left(1 - \frac{B}{2} \right) < 0.$$

Fig. 10 Fiber Orientation and the Modulus of Elasticity in Terms of Applied Stress

(ii) For $B < 2$, $B < 2A$

$$D = B^2 - B(4+3A) + 2A^2 + 5A + 3, \quad (17)$$

$$< -3(A+1) < 0.$$

As the value of B is ordinarily larger than 2, from $B > 2A$, we have

$$\frac{E_L}{2G_{LT}} - \nu_{LT} > \frac{E_L}{E_T} \quad (18)$$

Therefore,

$$2G_{LT} < E_L$$

When Eq. (19) is satisfied, E_L/E_X^* has maximum and therefore, E_X^*/E_L has minimum. We can obtain the fiber orientations when the value of E_X^*/E_L has minimum value for carbon fiber-reinforced plastics and glass fiber-reinforced plastics by above equation.

(i) For CFRP the mechanical properties are as follows;

$$E_L = 17000 \text{ kg/mm}^2,$$

$$E_T = 1500 \text{ kg/mm}^2,$$

$$G_{LT} = 400 \text{ kg/mm}^2,$$

$$\nu_{LT} = 0.24$$

Thus, $A = 11.33$ and $B = 42.02$.

Where, $\tan^2 \theta = 2.067$ and therefore,

when $\theta = 55.18^\circ$, the value of E_X^*/E_L reaches minimum value.

Fig. 11 Finite Element Breakdown at a Doubly Edge Notched Tension Specimen.

(ii) For GFRP the mechanical properties are as follows;

$$E_L = 3450 \text{ kg/mm}^2,$$

$$E_T = 1223 \text{ kg/mm}^2,$$

$$G_{LT} = 442 \text{ kg/mm}^2,$$

$$\nu_{LT} = 0.33$$

Thus, $A = 2,821$ and $B = 7.159$.

Where, $\tan^2 \theta = 3.399$ and therefore,

when $\theta = 61.55^\circ$, the value of E_x^*/E_L reaches minimum value.

As a result of the above, E_x^*/E_L reaches minimum when the degree of fiber orientation is about 50° or 60° . However, when the applied stress is large, the modulus of elasticity at that applied stress is not equal to the modulus of elasticity at low stresses. Therefore, Eq. (18) can not be satisfied at large applied stress and E_x^*/E_L does not have a minimum value.

Crack Propagation for Unidirectional Glassfiber Reinforced Plastics

It is well known that a crack in a unidirectionally fiber reinforced plastics propagates along the fiber. In this section, this crack propagation is investigated by using FV as finite element analysis with an element break down in Fig. 11. Fracture of element is determined by assumption that the element will be broken if FV in the element reaches 300. The calculated crack propagations are shown in Figs. 12, 13 and 14. The ratio of crack depth (a) to width of specimen (w) is 1/2. It is clear from these figures that the crack propagates along the glassfiber. The state of crack propagation in unidirectional glassfiber reinforced plastic with fiber orientation of 45° is remarkably similar to that observed experimentally.

Fig. 12 Crack Propagation in Unidirectional Fiber Reinforced Plastics at Low Stress ($\theta=90^\circ$)

Fig. 13 Crack Propagation in Unidirectional Fiber Reinforced Plastics at High Stress ($\theta=90^\circ$)

Discussions

In fiber reinforced plastics, the fracture patterns in tension are separated into the following three categories;

- (1) Fracture of fiber,
- (2) Shear fracture in laminated layers of fiber and resin,
- (3) Fracture of resin.

We must therefore consider the fracture pattern in simulating the mechanical behaviors for composite material. These fracture patterns can not be distinguished by looking at Fig. 8. By changing the coefficient of slider (a_x, a_y), the change in fracture pattern, as shown in Fig. 15, becomes distinguishable. Region (I) in Fig. 15 represents the pattern of the fiber fracture likewise region (II) represents the pattern of shear fracture in laminated layer and region (III) represents the pattern of the fracture of resin. Region (I) is also reduced when the coefficients of slider (a_x, a_y)

Fig. 14 Crack Propagation in Unidirectional Fiber Reinforced Plastic ($\theta=45^\circ$).

Fig. 15 Relation Between Fracture Stress and Fiber Orientation

are increased as shown in Fig. 16. This is why a_x and a_y indicate the degree of fiber and resin adhesion.

When the coefficients (a_x, a_y) are large, the fiber-resin adhesion is not perfect and therefore, the fracture strength is reduced.

As a result of this investigation on simulation, it became clear that Eq.(10) can be used as a fracture criterion for composite materials because fracture analysis by Poisson's ratio is in good agreement with the experimental results.

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